

THE ROLE OF PROVERBS EXPRESSING THE CONCEPT OF "LABOR" IN ENGLISH AND THEIR UZBEK EQUIVALENTS

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Abstract:

This article gives information about the proverbs which the word "labor" is expressed in proverbs and their equivalents in Uzbek language. In this article some proverbs are given and their analysis are given. The proverbs which are used the word "labor" are compared to the proverbs in Uzbek language and the equivalents are given. The article talks about the role and importance of the proverb genre in the English and Uzbek landscapes, and the fact that proverbs are considered a permanent object of research by linguists, historians, and ethnographers in many fields of linguistics.

Keywords: the concept, the labor, the proverb, linguistic, alliteration, genre, fluency, linguistic environment.

It is clear that when it comes to give a description to proverbs, it was always difficult for the scientists and scholars in every periods.

Some scientists even think that it is impossible to give a clear description for the proverbs. However, it is clear that the proverbs in every country they have got their own contribution to their country tradition and it is main part of the country. In addition, in every country they have got their own culture, politeness and history. By the help of the proverbs, this heritage will be left and informed for the future generation. Although the proverbs have got their own purpose in every language, we can see some similarities between them. In the Uzbek proverbs we can see some similarities in terms of their functions. For example, let's take one English proverb "first think, then speak" and in the Uzbek language the equivalents of this proverb will be given like this: "Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla". We can say that they are the same because when it comes to the meaning and the functions of these proverbs that they are the same.

Moreover, sometimes we can come across some proverbs that there are not their equivalents in both languages and it is difficult to translate them because of their traditional background. For instance, the proverb in Uzbek language, "Qizi borning, nozi bor". If we translate this proverb in English language in this way, it will bring some strangeness: who has a daughter that has a whim. So, it is suggested that we can translate in this way: Parents of the bride may be capricious (they can expose their own terms). Another Uzbek proverb is that "qassob moy qayg'usida, echki jon qayg'usida". We find the equivalents of this proverb, it will be given in this way: "The butcher grieves for bacon, and the goat - for its life".

In a conclusion we can say that the descriptions of proverbs should be appropriate for the nation's culture. For instance, in the English proverb "love and cough cannot be hidden. The equivalents of this proverb in the Uzbek language can be given in this way: "muhabbat va yo'talni yashirib bo'lmaydi". The correct version will be given in this way: "kasalni yashirsang isitmasi namoyon bo'ladi".

If we look another proverb in English language, it will be "doing is better than saying". If we translate this proverb in Uzbek language word by word, it will be given in this way: "Gapirgandan qilgan yaxshi" and in Uzbek language we will not come across this kind of proverb in Uzbek language. So, in Uzbek language the equivalents will be given with this proverb: "Gap bilguncha, ish bil". In these proverbs we can say that it will be better doing work than speaking more. In Uzbek language another equivalents will be given like this "So'zda bor amalda yo'q".

We can compare other English and Uzbek proverbs. For example, "business before pleasure". In Uzbek language we can translate "Hordiqdan oldin mehnat". But we can not say in

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this way. The equivalents of this proverb will be given with this proverb: “Mehnat, mehnatning tagi rohat”.

These proverbs may have got their equivalents in both languages. However, we can not use the way in the context. Because it will bring some misunderstanding in terms of semantics and methodological balance. The expressiveness will differ according to their meaning and they will be used in different situations and actions.

In conclusion, we can say that the proverbs which expresses the concept “labor” in Uzbek and English languages can describe how to be hardworking and persistent for the any situation. By the helping of analysing these progresses, we can be aware of the country’s traditions and their culture.

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